

Criteria for Morphological Justification of Surgical Treatment of Patients With Thyrotoxicosis

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Abstract: *Relevance. Interventions for relapses of toxic goiter forms are characterized by technical complexity, and for multiple and multiple relapses, tactical problems arise regarding the scope and nature of surgical intervention. Material and methods. The material of the study was the results of the study and surgical treatment of 112 patients with toxic goiter forms. In the morphological diagnosis of toxic goiter, the informative value of TIAB was 88.3%, EBI-94.4%, a combination of these factors methods increased their informative content to 98.1%. Introduction of morphological diagnostics of thyroid tissue changes in patients with toxic goiter forms into clinical practice made it possible to choose the optimal amount of surgical intervention. Research results. The developed algorithm for choosing the volume of surgical intervention for toxic goiter forms, taking into account the data of the conclusion of TIAB and EBI, improved the results of treatment by reducing the frequency of unsatisfactory results in the long-term postoperative period from 18.9% to 4.1%.*

Keywords: *morphological examination, intraoperative express biopsy, fine needle puncture aspiration biopsy.*

Introduction

The scope of surgical intervention for toxic goiter forms can vary from resection of the affected lobe to complete thyroidectomy. According to the literature, 96.8% of patients with recurrent toxic goiter had organ-preserving primary surgery, but the greatest number of relapses is observed in patients with multi-node lesions [3,6]. Surgical interventions for relapses of toxic goiter forms are characterized by high technical complexity, and with multiple and multiple relapses, serious problems arise in choosing the scope and nature of the operation [1,4]. A modern analysis of the literature reveals the existence of several opposite approaches to the treatment of toxic goiter forms [4,5]. The lack of a unified diagnostic algorithm that would take into account modern classification approaches makes it difficult to identify key criteria and justify the choice of the optimal surgical option [2,3]. One of the most urgent directions is to improve the quality of treatment of patients with toxic goiter forms by choosing the most effective surgical method and developing strategies to reduce the frequency of thyrotoxicosis relapses. Objective: to optimize the treatment and diagnostic algorithm for toxic goiter forms, taking into account the morphological structure of thyroid tissue.

Material and methods of research. The research material is as follows:

results of the study and surgical treatment of 112 patients with toxic goiter forms operated on in surgical departments

multidisciplinary clinic of Samarkand State Medical University and City Clinical Hospital No. 1 in period from 20-1616 to 202.33 г.

All patients in the comparison group (n=52) with toxic goiter forms whose thyrotoxic status was medically reduced to euthyroidism (45

86.5% of patients) and grade I thyrotoxicosis (7 patients-13.5%) were operated on. 32 (61.5%) patients underwent subtotal subfascial strumectomy, 12 (23.1%) - subtotal subfascial surgery.

resection of one and wedge-shaped resection of the contralateral lobe of the thyroid gland (thyroid gland), 6 (11.5%) patients underwent hemithyroidectomy and 2 (3.8%) - partial resection of the thyroid gland.

The best results of surgical treatment of patients in the comparison group were observed in 37 (71.1%) patients, with a follow-up period of 2 to 10 years. Recurrent goiter was detected in 7 (18.9%) patients, hypothyroidism - in 1 (2.7%).

Morphological studies of thyroid gland tissues were performed,

52 patients of the comparison group received during the operation, a total of 267 micro-preparations were studied.

In the study of drugs in 78% of cases, the development of connective tissue of 2-3 degrees prevailed (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Microphotogram
Microphotogram of the thyroid preparation. Patient P., 41 years old. Pronounced overgrowth of connective tissue. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification x100.

Fig. 2. Microphotogram
Microphotogram of the thyroid preparation. Patient V., 36 years old. Small follicles lined with low or cylindrical epithelium. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Zoom in x400.

Epithelial changes were expressed in the appearance of small follicles lined with low cylindrical epithelium. Proliferative changes were weak or absent (Figure 2). Thus, this histological picture indicated the development of sclerotic processes and weak proliferative changes with a low level of autoimmune thyroid stimulation. In the study of thyroid micropreparations in 22% of cases, the characteristic phenomena were epithelial proliferation with the formation of papillae, its cells were cubic in shape (Fig. 3).

<p>3. Microphotogram Microphotogram of the thyroid preparation. Patient S., 49 years old. Epithelial proliferation, papillary formation. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Magnification x200.</p>	<p>Fig. 4. Microphotogram Microphotogram of the thyroid preparation. Patient T., 52 years old. Large follicles with a large amount of liquid colloid. Loose stroma. Hematoxylin and eosin staining. Zoom in x100.</p>
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In all preparations, a large amount of colloid with intensive resorption was noted (Fig. 4). The degree of development of connective tissue it was insignificant.

In 7 (18.9%) cases with relapse of toxic goiter (out of 37 patients of the comparison group followed in the long-term postoperative period), a retrospective analysis of morphological studies of thyroid tissue revealed epithelial proliferation with papilla formation, as well as a large amount of colloid with intensive resorption. Lymphoid infiltration, plasma cells, and macrophages were detected equally in all preparations, which may indicate a general autoimmune nature of the disease.

Thus, the development of morphological changes in thyroid tissue directly depends on the degree of activity of the autoimmune process. With a high level of autoimmune stimulation, morphological changes are observed, indicating the predominance of epithelial proliferation and transformation processes. This, in turn, contributes to the development of hyperplastic processes in the thyroid tissue, which, against the background of persistent high autoimmune stimulation, can lead to a relapse of thyrotoxicosis during resection techniques. It follows that the retention of thyroid tissue in the presence of

such a histological picture is impractical.

With the detection of a pronounced process of sclerosis of thyroid tissue and weak proliferative changes, further progression of the disease after performing thyroid resection, it is unlikely, since replacement of follicles with sclerotic tissue does not contribute to the further development of hyperplasia and hyperfunction of the tissue on the thyroid gland.

low titer of autoimmune stimulation.

In this connection, all patients of the main group (n = 60) underwent a fine-needle aspiration biopsy (TIAB) of the thyroid gland before surgery. If the patient had several nodes, cellular punctates were aspirated and each of them was examined separately. TIAB was performed under the control of Profocus 2202 and Minifocus 1402 devices manufactured by BK Medical (Denmark) with linear sensors (6-12 MHz) (Figure 5).

5. TIAB under ultrasound control.	6. Applying the aspirate to the slide.
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In the presence of a node with a solid ultrasonic structure, the material was taken from the center and periphery of the node. In solid nodes with a cystic component, the material was aspirated from a solid site. In cystic nodes, material was collected from the node tissue along the cyst periphery. Each node was dotted with at least two different points.

The resulting glass products were stained according to the May–Grunwald–Giemsa method

6). Cytological studies were performed by light microscopy, in some cases, according to indications, immunocytochemical studies were performed, and if there were cyst contents in the aspirate, liquid cytology was used. Cytological examination of 37 (61.7%) patients showed the appearance of small follicles lined with low cylindrical epithelium with connective tissue overgrowth without proliferative changes (Fig. 7).

7. Patient B., 44 years old, 2017 Cytological conclusion of TIAB: Pronounced overgrowth of connective tissue	Fig. 8. Patient Zh. 44 years old, 2018 Cytological conclusion of TIAB: Proliferation of follicular epithelium in the node, vacuolated colloid
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In 18 (30.0%) cases, cytological examination showed epithelial proliferation with papilla formation, a large amount of colloid with intensive resorption, and the degree of connective tissue development was insignificant (Fig. 8). In 5 (8.3%) patients, the drug was not informative. A retrospective evaluation of the results of this group of patients showed that these were patients with atypical and hard -to-reach thyroid nodules. As a rule, this explains the insufficient amount of cytological material in the aspirate, the so-called "empty smear".

Out of 55 (91.7%) examinees with informative drugs, the results were as follows:

cytological and histological studies coincided in 53 (88.3%) patients

Results of the study did not match in 2 (3.3%) patients. Thus, TIAB in toxic goiter forms is a highly informative, minimally invasive method of preoperative morphological diagnostics that allows us to verify structural changes in the thyroid gland. Based on the results obtained, we can conclude that TIAB is informative at the preoperative stage, which in our study was 88.3%.

In addition to TIAB, 54 (90.0%) patients in the main group underwent intraoperative rapid biopsy (EBI) based on "frozen" (cryostatic) sections obtained during the operation and allowing them to choose the optimal volume of surgery.

However, the amount of material studied was very limited, and the cryostat sections were significantly inferior in quality to the sections obtained after pouring the material into paraffin. Therefore, the indications for EBI had certain limitations. In our study, we performed EBI according to the following indications: - in patients with uninformative TIAB material and with grade III thyrotoxicosis before a drug-induced decrease in thyrostatic status. In 35 (64.8%) patients examined, the results of rapid biopsy and postoperative histological studies coincided (Fig.

(5.5%) did not match.

9. Patient R., 42, 2017, with thyroid EBV. Node active proliferating goiter with varying shape and size of follicles, focus of hemorrhage and accumulation of hemosiderophages, coloration hematoxylin-eosin, 20x magnification.

Based on the results obtained, we can conclude информативности that intraoperative rapid biopsy is informative, which in our study was 94.4%.

Taking into account the data of TIAB and EBI in the main group of patients, surgical tactics for toxic goiter forms were differentiated. Taking into account the factors that influenced the results of treatment of patients in the comparison group, we разработали developed a point system for choosing the volume of surgery for toxic goiter forms.

Patients with a total score of up to 9 points received the following tests:

hemithyroidectomy. This group consisted of patients who, as a rule, had a small toxic thyroid adenoma (up to 6 cm in diameter) without proliferative cells in TIAB and EB. Subtotal thyroid resection was performed in patients with a score of 10 to 12 points with toxic goiter forms резекцию ЩЖ. Patients with a score of more than 12 points, who had foci of varying degrees of thyroid tissue proliferation with TIAB and EBI, underwent radical operations - thyroidectomy. The developed program for scoring factors influencing the choice of surgery in patients with toxic goiter forms made it possible to choose the optimal amount of surgery, taking into account the clinical – and morphological course of the disease. Based on the clinical course of the disease and in accordance with the program for determining the choice of surgical tactics for toxic goiter forms, we developed and implemented a therapeutic and tactical management of patients with toxic goiter forms in clinical practice (Fig.

Figure 10. Therapeutic and tactical algorithm for managing patients with toxic diseases forms of goiter.

In the main group, 40 (66.7%) patients underwent subtotal surgery.

thyroid resection, 19 (31.7%) patients with significant thyroid tissue proliferation and recurrent toxic goiter underwent thyroidectomy and 1 (1.7%) patient underwent hemithyroidectomy. Long-term results were observed in 49 patients, relapse was noted in 2 (4.1%) cases.

Conclusions.

1. In the morphological diagnosis of toxic goiter, the informative value of TIAB was 88.3%, EBI-94.4%, and the combination of these methods increased the informative value to 98.1%. Introduction to clinical practice

practice of morphological diagnostics of thyroid tissue changes

The study of breast cancer in patients with toxic goiter forms allowed us to choose the optimal volume of surgical intervention.

2. Organ-preserving operations for proliferative changes in thyroid tissue in patients with toxic goiter forms are not effective and contribute to the recurrence of the disease.

3. The developed algorithm for choosing the volume of surgical intervention in toxic goiter forms, taking into account the data of the conclusion of TIAB and EBI, made it possible to improve the results of treatment by reducing the frequency of unsatisfactory results in the long-term postoperative period. in the period from 18.9% to 4.1%.

Reference

1. Ismailov S. I., Kamildzhanova B. R. Features of quality of life in patients operated on for nodular and multi-nodular goiter. 2015, No. 19, pp. 270-274.
2. Ismailov S. I., Samadova U. S. Budushchie posledstviya khirurgicheskogo lecheniya uzlogogo gob [Future consequences of surgical treatment of nodular goiter]. Molodoy issledovatel': vyzovy i perspektivy: sb. st. po materialam CIII Mezhdunarodnoi nauchno-prakticheskoi konferentsii "Young Researcher: Challenges and Prospects". - M.- 2019. - № 3(103).
3. Gulov M. K. Clinical and morphological picture of multi-node euthyroid goiter // Avicenna's Messenger. - 2017. - Vol. 19. - No. 1.
4. Principles of diagnosis and treatment of nodular goiter // Medical Council, 2016, No. 3.

5. Makarov I. V., Galkin R. A., Akhmataliev T. H. Tactics of surgical treatment of patients with thyroid diseases // International Scientific Research Journal. - 2016. - № 7-3 (49). - P. 77-80.
6. Kononenko S. N. Surgical tactics for benign nodular formations of the thyroid gland. - 2011. - No. 11. - p. 24-27.
7. Kaloeva A. A. Morphology and morphogenesis of endemic goiter: abstract of the dissertation of the Candidate of Medical Sciences. Saratov, 2015, 22 p. (in Russian)
8. Belokonev V. I., Starostina A. A., Kovaleva Z. V., Selezneva E. V. Substantiation of approaches to the selection of patients with thyroid diseases for surgical treatment. 2012, vol. 20, No. 4, pp. 17-22.
9. Gozibekov Zh. I., Yusupalieva D. B., Tilavova Yu. M. Long-term results of surgical treatment of thyroid nodules // Achievements in science and education. – 2019. – № 7 (48).
10. Shin D.Y., Lee Y.K., Kim K.J. Thyroid cancers with benign-looking sonographic features have different lymph node metastatic risk and histologic subtypes according to nodule size // Endocr. Pathol. - 2014. - Vol. 25. - N 4. - P. 378-384.